

THE ROLE OF PUPPET THEATRE IN THE ART OF COMEDY AND CLOWNING**Aliyeva Nazokat Shavkat qizi**

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Scientific Supervisor: Associate Professor **A. Abduxalilov****Abstract**

The art of comedy and the art of clowning have served for centuries as a means of making people laugh, sharing positive emotions, and critically highlighting certain situations in social life. These art forms have been widespread among the people and have manifested themselves in various forms: from stage performances to street shows, from circuses to puppet theatre performances. In particular, puppet theatre occupies a special place in the development of this art. This article discusses the history of the development of the arts of comedy and clowning, the formation of puppet theatre in Central Asia, and its significance in these art forms.

Keywords: comedy, comedian, humorist, clown, mockery, clowning, performance, Afandi, anecdote, actor, situation, laughter, satire, folklore, ritual performance, mythological characters, itinerant performer, puppet, image, artist.

When discussing the origins of the arts of comedy and clowning, it becomes clear that they are among the most ancient forms of artistic activity in human history. Initially, these art forms appeared as entertainment during religious ceremonies and acts of worship. In Ancient Greece and Rome, clowns were popular among the people and were known as actors performing in the comedy genre. During the Middle Ages in Europe, clowns served in royal courts, becoming not only sources of laughter but also individuals who expressed political criticism. The Fool's words to King Lear

Fool: "Truth is like a frightening dog; it is constantly driven outside. Flattery, however, is like a greyhound: even if it stinks and festers, it lives in the place of honor in the house..."

If I may be heard. Keep your wealth a secret, Even if you know much, speak little. Do not lend excessively, Ride a horse, do not walk on foot. Even if you know, do not say 'I know', Gather possessions, do not spend them. Do not drink wine, do not indulge in pleasure, Sit only in your house. Then the account will be good,

*It will exceed twenty...¹ Through their irony, satire, and humorous performances, they not only uplifted the people's spirits but also expressed protest against social inequalities. Among the peoples of the East, particularly in Central Asia, the arts of comedy and clowning were also widespread. Clowns, tightrope walkers, and cheerful performers took part in local and national festivals, folk performances, and market-day entertainments. They mainly performed through improvisation, creating humorous scenes based on the daily social life of the people and the negative phenomena existing in society. During the khanate period of the nineteenth century, the content of clowning and comic performance became richer, its satirical sharpness intensified, and the range of themes and genres expanded and diversified. Like a magnifying mirror, clowning and comedy truthfully reflected all aspects of khanate life in satirical colors.²

Now let us consider the emergence of puppet theatre art in Central Asia. Puppet theatre has existed in Central Asia since ancient times, and its earliest forms were connected with folklore, religious ritual performances, and mythological characters. A person wearing a carnival mask can already be considered a half-puppet. If that person is also an actor, he becomes a puppeteer because, while attempting to animate an inanimate mask, he performs more effectively through puppet techniques.³ Historical sources report that among the ancient Khorezmians, Sogdians, and other ancient peoples, religious and legendary scenes were presented with the help of ritual puppets. During the fourteenth and fifteenth centuries, puppet performances were frequently seen during street entertainments and festivities in Mawarannahr and Khorezm. Puppet theatres were

usually itinerant, with performers traveling from city to city presenting shows. Their performances mainly reflected everyday life, folk tales, humorous situations, and social criticism. Puppets were made of wood, cloth, and leather, and their movements were controlled by simple strings, rods, or hand manipulation. Stage works created through these simple techniques were welcomed with great interest by the people.

Puppet theatre can be regarded as one of the branches of the arts of comedy and clowning. Both art forms serve to attract audiences through laughter, encourage reflection, and provide entertainment. There are many similarities between puppet performances and the folk professional theatre of clowning. When clowns used masks in their performances, they effectively transformed into puppets, since they were compelled to employ the expressive means of stage puppets that alternately remained motionless and came to life.⁴ The characters depicted in puppet theatre performances often appear in the form of comedians or clowns. Through their simple yet deeply meaningful speeches, they discuss social vices and certain human shortcomings. For example, the appearance of the character Afandi in puppet theatre demonstrates how closely these art forms are interconnected. Afandi always makes the audience laugh and marvel through humorous yet intelligent jokes, while also teaching valuable lessons. This characteristic constitutes the fundamental essence of the art of comedy. Puppet theatre is not only entertaining but also educational in significance. Performances designed especially for children play an invaluable role in shaping their aesthetic tastes and developing their moral values. Through puppet characters portraying comedians, children are taught to distinguish good from evil and are encouraged to value labor, friendship, kindness, and compassion.

At times, puppets also satirized dogmatic religious figures. Naturally, such performances did not escape the attention of religious groups. Puppet theatre was sometimes called a “devil’s game,” and puppeteers were accused of challenging God’s work. Such attitudes often led to the humiliation and marginalization of those involved in this art form.⁵ The professional development of puppet theatre in Uzbekistan dates back to the beginning of the twentieth century. In 1939, the Uzbekistan State Puppet Theatre was established in Tashkent. Incorporating traditions of comic performance, this theatre created productions on a variety of themes, including fairy tales, socio-political life, and historical events. Today, puppet theatres operate in various regions throughout the Republic. In all of them, elements of comedy and clowning are widely used. Through laughter, humor, and engaging plots, important ideas are conveyed to both children and adults. In conclusion, it can be said that the arts of comedy and clowning are closely interconnected with puppet theatre. Both are closely related to the lifestyle and everyday life of the people and possess the ability to influence society through humor while remaining attentive to social issues.

The role of puppet theatre in this regard is invaluable, especially from educational, aesthetic, and cultural-enlightenment perspectives. It should be recognized not only as an art form but also as a part of the cultural heritage of the people.

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